

The Role of Requirements in Open Source IT Innovation

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Abstract. The requirements process is a collection of activities in software engineering which purpose it is to define the functionality and properties of a future system-to-be, taking into account the environment and the problem domain. However simple as it may sound, it is a difficult undertaking, and it would seem that OS requirements are handled in a particular manner. Further, requirements can be seen as being intimately linked to IT innovation as representing attempts to create a certain vision of a future IT system. If open source organisations are as different to traditional ones as it is often claimed, then it is likely that requirements are handled differently and thus play a different role in influencing IT innovation. This essay thus proposes the study of the role of requirements in open source IT innovation.

Key words: requirements engineering, requirements, innovation, open source

1 Introduction

Requirements are often seen as representing an attempt to define a future IT system. This may sound simple, but as early as Brooks' time, deciding on the requirements was the "hardest, single part of building an IT system" [1]. Since requirements attempt to define IT, it can be supposed that they have some link to IT innovation. Further, requirements in OS seem to be handled differently than traditional methodologies suggest [2], or offer an alternative to software development [3].

To which extent does this hold true, and under what conditions? What is the role of OS requirements IT innovation?

This essay proposes the study of the role of requirements in OS IT innovation. Section 2 presents a brief review of the literature. Section 3 exposes the problem statement. Section 4 presents the conceptual framework, and finally, section 5 proposes a research design.

2 Research Background

2.1. Traditional Requirements Engineering

Traditionally, requirements are seen as an engineering activity. Requirements Engineering (RE) is an essential activity in the software engineering process. RE is concerned with “a branch of software engineering concerned with the real-world goals for, functions of, and constraints on software systems [...] and the relationship of these factors” [4]. Jackson, has a similar definition where he describes two interrelated elements: the machine and the world. The machine is the software, and the world is the context and environment [5, 6]. Since the world is the context and the environment, it also represents the problem domain from which goals can be elicited and with which the machine can interact to achieve some requirements. Hence, the *raison d’être* of any program lies entirely in the problem domain, the world. Understanding and modelling the problem domain is difficult, with some researchers arguing that it is impossible [7].

Requirements are not so much found as they are engineered [8]. This does not mean that requirements are “made up”, but that they need to be elicited with techniques and reasoned about by people from different backgrounds. Thus, they do not have an independent existence, but are in fact socially constructed. Techniques are useful to engineers so that they can elicit requirements by exploring the problem domain; what can be for them a “*terra incognita*”.

Traditional computer science approaches to system development is generally criticised for being positivist in nature and making unfounded assumptions concerning the organisational context [9]. Solutions to problems in the development of systems are typically prescriptive and argue for more engineering techniques and modeling methods [8]. This concern for engineering techniques is historically bounded to a time when programs were seen as simple Turing machines, sequentially computing well defined algorithms in order to solve unambiguous problems. This type of literature views the world as ordered, or rather chaotic in the Greek sense of the word, simply awaiting ordering.

Typical RE processes include four principal activities: requirements elicitation, requirements specification (or modeling) and analysis, negotiating and agreeing on requirements, and finally communicating and documenting requirements [10, 11].

2.2. Requirements in OS

The problem is that methodologies can take certain assumptions that can influence the success of the requirements engineering process and thereby, the product itself. The assumptions can stem from the epistemological perspective taken by the field in order to simplify the “messiness” of the ambiguous world [12]. One such supposition concerns the organisational context in which methods are

prescribed. The fact that information systems can drift shows the volatility of modeling the world and the importance of the context in which they are put to use [7]. Can it really be assumed that the same method will yield the same causal results in two different contexts? Existing literature also would seem to deny this [2, 13, 14].

Open source would certainly seem to present some interesting differences. The history and culture is largely rooted in academia where the idea of cooperation and openness was strong [15, 16]. From culture, this form of viewing software transformed into an ideology, where the freedom of access to the code and modification is in fact a moral choice or right [16, 17]. These traits are enforced by an open license [17], and appear to allow for widespread collaboration without the need for formal ties. Shared, then, amongst all OS projects is a generic hacker culture [15], that lives along the particular culture latent in any OS project, principally formed up by its community [2].

The community in OS can form an integral part in the development of IT systems innovation, but also in the proposition and elicitation of requirements. Indeed, by effectively allowing anyone, including users, to make changes to software, the project can respond to an increasing heterogeneity of needs and demand [18]. Interestingly, users are not passive anymore, but rather have the potential of becoming full fledged actors in the creation of IT innovation. Thus, the success of an OS project will, at least partly, reveal the market potential that exists for that type of IT system since OS effort is partly borne by users who can also be developers themselves [15]. Thus, part of the market and requirements research appears to be done “on the fly”, or post-hoc, by users of the system themselves proposing functionality [19].

It is often assumed that the source of requirements in OS is a developer’s scratch (Raymond, 2001), and that there seemingly is no project planning [13]. A requirement thus comes from a particular need, and its subsequent development responds to the specific need and motivation of a contributor or user, and not necessarily of a market as would a commercial application [18]. If the particular need of a person is shared with others, then there is a likelihood that the project will gain development impetus and interest [15]. In this sense, OS projects go through a ‘natural selection’ process. Other sources of requirements are bug reports, change requests and feature enhancement from mailing lists, wikis and usenet newsgroups.

There are other sources of requirements. German identifies five for the GNOME project: project leaders, reference applications, discussions through, for example, mailing lists, prototypes and post-hoc requirements when developers who wish a final feature to be included in the release [20].

In terms of specification, requirements appear to be defined by informal descriptions of the system-to-be and are specified, analysed and documented in terms of narratives through online “webs of discourse” [2]. These webs of discourse are

trails of discussion concerning the informal requirements, and which help making sense of what it is that should be implemented.

Another consequence of such openness is the ability for large scale peer reviewing, analysis and negotiation of requirements. In terms of bugs, peer reviewing with just one more person drastically increases the reliability of the code [15]. For this reason, many agile development methods advice the use of peer reviewing. Open source here goes further. By allowing the development artefacts and the code to be opened to anyone, peer reviewing can be done at a larger scale, leading to Raymond's Linus' law: "the more eyeballs, the less bugs" [15]. Could this also be true for requirements? If the more people implicate themselves actively, then can the requirements process end up with more accurate requirements? Also, the fact that the source code is open, that contributions and peer reviewing is encouraged, work on open source projects also appear to be, in many cases, highly decentralised collaborations [21].

Whether a request is actually carried out depends on the OS project, and the process associated with the selection of requirements. In Apache, developers (especially core ones) need to be convinced of the usefulness of the feature request [13]. Other OS projects can instead use voting systems. The amount and quality of information that is given by the requestor can also be seen as filters. If key information is missing, then the request has less chances of being considered [13]. Other OS projects such as Mozilla.org, however, also provide a roadmap outlining functionality for future releases [13].

2.3. Linking Requirements to IT Innovation

There are numerous studies on innovation. Some have looked at IT innovation from an organisational perspective [22, 23], while others have looked at user created innovation [24, 25]. Other studies have looked at the innovation process itself, but from an economical and motivational perspective [26-28].

Open innovation advocates for the openness and sharing of innovation which, it is hoped, will increase innovation and the creation of new markets since ideas can be freely exploited by anyone without major legal constraints [26, 27]. Moreover, if one believes that the diffusion of innovation stems from imitation [24], then the fact that the code, and therefore, requirements and functionality is open and free to be copied and reused, encourages innovation.

Open innovation is not necessarily synonymous with open source. It could very well be used by traditional organisations. But the similarities between the OS organisational characteristics, and this innovation model are numerous. Indeed, no impediment to copying, to redistributing or to building upon existing innovation. The only constraint that some OS licenses might impose is the necessity to contribute improvements or innovations back to the community [29]. For OS projects, the community would form an integral part in the development of IT systems innovation.

Indeed, it is one of the proposed reasons as to why open innovation, by effectively allowing anyone, including users, to make changes to software can respond to an increasing heterogeneity of demand [18].

These meta-models look at innovation from an economical and organisational point of view, and in so doing can lose sight of the IT artefact [30]. IT itself is more than a simple black-boxed entity; it can be quite complex, especially in the process of IT creation. The subprocess of Requirements Engineering, is composed of actors - stakeholders, physical artefacts (specifications, design models, etc...), but also of implicit or hidden desires and knowledge that can be expressed at any moment of the software development process. Further, if requirements define the functionality and properties of an IT system, could the management of requirements have repercussions on IT innovation?

2.4. Discussion

This essay has presented a review of software development and the requirements process as being polarised between traditional software engineering and open source software. However, the differences might be much greyer in practice. It seems important now to mitigate this polarisation.

Some influential computer science literature, based on Agile methodologies such as eXtreme Programming, in fact, assumes that change is inevitable, and thus that prescribed techniques must be flexible enough to reposition the definition of the software (requirements for developers) to the most current and correct understanding [31]. Although it is also based upon prescriptive indications, this stream of literature in software engineering has recognised the complexity and ambiguity of an ever changing world and proposes ways to reduce complexity and increase flexibility by making, say, requirements more informal.

Another critique of this polarisation could come from a recent paper that claims that open source software is becoming more like its closed source opposite and vice versa [32]. Also, even though positivist literature abounds with examples of methods and claims of good practice, it seems that they are mostly ideals [33], that either need to be faked purposely [34], or altogether unattainable.

But what is open source? And for that matter, what is a traditional organisation? These are quite complex questions, and some aspects often described as open source development can be found in traditional organisations as well. The existence of a strong community also exists outside open source. Apple and the App Store, for example, have created an important crowd sourcing environment with the creation of applications that can meet a wide variety of needs.

Open source projects can also have a strong link to traditional organisations. Mozilla, for example, is described as a hybrid [13]. Do hybrid open source project handle requirements differently than non-hybrids?

Does OS simply refer to the openness of the code and the development artefacts, unconcerned? If this reasoning is followed, then, the only difference

between a closed IT system and an open one is a legal or ideological matter. Open source would therefore closely resemble to crowd sourcing models, but with the source code open. There are, however, some indications from the literature that this openness does bring some changes in the development, practices and management of IT systems [2, 3, 14, 35]. It would be interesting to investigate to which extent this holds true, and under what conditions.

3 Problem Statement

The research question is thus focused on understanding the role that requirements play in OS IT innovation. In this sense, the agenda centers on understanding how requirements are handled within open source projects for the development of IT innovation. The innovation referred to here is not to be understood solely in terms of software, but also in terms of the development practices used. This research induces a second layer of related sub-research questions. Firstly, what is the relationship between requirements and IT innovation. Can IT innovation be promoted or hindered through the management of requirements? Secondly, what are the differences between OSRP and traditional RE? Is OS requirements handled as is claimed by the literature? Are there any exceptions? For example, it is imaginable that requirements in health systems could be handled less informally given the importance of safety and security requirements. Is there some nature of engineering in the OSRP, if so, how different is it compared to traditional RE? Thirdly, how does the “openness” concept influence the requirements process? Is there some typicality in the OSRP that can be attributed to OS characteristics? How does this play in terms of the community, the various users and the possible implication or sponsorship of traditional companies?

The aim of the study is not to edict prescriptive statements of good practice in open source, but rather investigating the situated handling of requirements in their context.

4 Theoretical Framework

Following Crotty’s taxonomy, we take a phenomenological theoretical stance from which to analyse the requirements [36]. Studying the open source requirements process and its relation to IT innovation from a phenomenological perspective allows for the study of how requirements and its processes are dealt with on a day to day basis. As Ciborra says, “the phenomenological perspective can help us recognise and value the importance of bricolage versus the over-inflated role of method and planning in strategic applications” [12, p.21]. The concepts of emergence, bricolage and drifting are put up against attempts to plan, document and specify requirements. This section briefly introduces these concepts.

Hypomnemata is a concept from old Greece and mentioned by Foucault in one of his interviews [37], when the Greeks kept special agendas that were useful to them. These were not used for keeping records of what had happened, but instead for how they might better tackle similar future problems [37]. These agendas had an essential role to play in the organisation of one self and Foucault claims the emergence of this technology as being as disruptive for ancient Greece as the invention of the computer. This material memory, Foucault argues, became an important element for the culture of the self since hypomnemata recorded accounts that could eventually help in the guidance of future actions [37]. In what concerns requirements, these could be specifications, models and documentations which act in the same way for IT innovation by providing guidelines for future actions. Hypomnemata, however, do not need to be fixed documents whose main purpose is one of guidance. It could well be that, for example, the proposal of a feature creates a certain debate in the community, and that once written, the debate will constrain future related features, with say, references by authors to the original discussion. Although this is a hypothetical example, it is reasonable to envisage that there exists heated discussions concerning certain requirements, and since all is made public in OS projects, OS requirements could possess certain characteristics that endure in time. Hypomnemata, therefore, are not necessarily central requirements document, but could also well be previous discussions that could constrain future debates.

On the other hand, the phenomenological concepts drawn from Ciborra of emergence and the related concepts of improvisation, bricolage, drifting, on the contrary, posit that the world cannot be modeled given the complexity of the world [38, 39]. As aforementioned, the concepts can help in understanding the importance of the spontaneous, the unexpected and the messiness of the world. The concepts of emergence, bricolage, tinkering and drifting are closely related. Analysed as moods, instead of mindsets [40], they represent a bottom-up approach to create emergent, and possibly drifting innovation by the understanding of local needs and available resources. The emergent results of bricolage can be surprising, probably because of their bottom-up mentality. Another concept that could help understand the tension between emergence and hypomnemata in context is hospitality [12].

The tension zone between the emergence, drifting and bricolage conflicts with the need to control and direct. However, given the appearing informality in the treatment of requirements in OS, then could it be that the participants, in fact, embrace a methodology of change, with elements of requirements drifting? The requirements handling process could well be seen as a technology in itself, in which case, the process could be accepted, or worked around [41], or if there are attempts to rationalise the requirements process. The informality of requirements therefore leads to the impression that they can have an inchoate aspect with entropic properties. They can easily be changed through discussion, and the purpose of the IT software can be redefined. If, on the other hand, they are written down, with explicit intentions to convince, and ultimately plan for requirements, then these hypomnemata could make the requirements process context more constraining and focused on controlling, coordinating and planning functionality.

Moreover, it is possible, for example, for a requirement to be created spontaneously, and for it to be progressively crystallised, becoming less malleable and achieving a certain hard status through, possibly, collective planning.

5 Proposed Research Design

This section presents a brief account of the planned empirical investigation. In summary, the plan consists of explorative, multiple case studies on projects spanning different market sectors. The data collection methods center around electronic archival exploration, supported by interviews that aim to address specific issues as informed by the archival exploration. The research planned should be qualitative so as to study the phenomena in context [42], but the use of quantitative methods are also planned as support.

Case studies are useful in studying requirements in Open Source for several reasons. Firstly, they provide the opportunity to study requirements in a context, as contemporary events, but also in a larger, historical time frame [43, 44]. Also, events surrounding requirements cannot be controlled, which rules out the experimental research method [43, 44]. Given the specificities of OS projects, depending on many contextual factors, such as the market sector or project history or contexts of use, and therefore, the expectation of different results, it would seem that a multiple case study approach is appropriate (Yin 2003). Further, it is hoped that the assumptions on OS software could be tested in various environments, making multiple case studies a desirable approach [43]. The use of case studies in OS research is extensive [2, 13, 20, 45-47].

Four suggested projects are foreseen: Moodle, OpenEHR, OpenOffice.org and BOINC (Berkeley Open Infrastructure for Network Computing). Moodle is a widely used educational course management software. OpenEHR is an open specification standard for the management of patient health data in electronic health records. Interestingly, it attempts to model and build a high-level specification of electronic health records that then can be instantiated to context specific clinical environments. It is hoped that the open specification is flexible enough to accommodate differences in business processes, but at the time providing benefits from interoperability and standards. OpenOffice.org is aimed at providing an OS office suite alternative, and is thus intended to fulfill the role of an open competitor to, principally, MS Office. BOINC is a middleware grid computing software.

The projects were chosen according to various criteria. First, it was decided to avoid the typical success stories, such as Mozilla, Linux and Apache, which have already been studied to some extent. Out of the four proposed cases, in fact, only the OpenOffice.org is a mainstream desktop application. The remaining three pertain to some form of niche sector. Following from this, the participants to the projects will likely have different backgrounds, interests and knowledge in IT development. It is probable then that the participants in Moodle will have a strong academic

background, nurses and doctors will be involved in OpenEHR and BOINC of physicists and scientists. The choice of the projects is therefore dictated by their differences rather than by their actual aims.

Regarding data collection, two methods are envisaged: archival exploration and interviews, both appropriate for case studies and allow for construct validity [43, 44].

Archival exploration represents a natural way of studying Open source projects given the general commitment to openness and traceability [15]. There are various sources from which requirements can be elicited: mailing lists, wikis, todo lists, requirements specifications or even bug tracker tools. These provide an unbiased account of the quotidian dealings of requirements. Analysing these allows for the qualification of the construction of requirements and the overall IT innovation process as being either emergent or more focused on planning the overall IT system.

Interviews, on the other hand, could provide second hand accounts on motivation, reasoning and backgrounds which would help the interpretation of the meaning of certain requirements or how they were formulated, or simply help understand the subject area better. Interviews would be semi structured as this provides a good level of flexibility [48]. It would be useful to have a good mix of participants corresponding to the following categories: engaged developer, project governance member, owners of a coding module, non-coding members who participate often, and finally, non-coding members who do not participate often. This would allow to take into account the participants' backgrounds and their possible influence on requirements.

6 Conclusion

The aim of this essay was to present a research proposal concerning the role of requirements in OS IT innovation. This essay first briefly reviewed the research areas involved and presented a theoretical framework to the proposed problem statement. Finally, a research design was proposed.

The expected contributions from this work then are to, firstly, provide a better understanding of the RE process in OS. Secondly, to better understand the relation between the RE and the IT innovation process.

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